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Sustainable Oxide/Oxide ceramic composites with atomic oxygen protection for VLEO satellite applications

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I. Introduction

Background

❖ Oxide-Oxide ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) By raw materials

- Non-oxide ceramics
 - Alumina Nitride
 - Silicon Nitride
 - Silicon Carbide
- Oxide ceramics
 - Alumina oxide
 - Zirconia oxide
 - Boron and Mullite oxide

Ceramics

<CMC prepeg and developed products^[1]> Ceramic matrix composites

High strength and modulus

High-temperature stability in oxidation

Ultra-high temp CMC (UHTCMC) may use borides, carbides and nitrides of transition metals like zirconium, hafnium, tantalum, etc.

UHTCMC		COMMERCIAL FIBER PRODUCERS	
Ta/C	3890°C	SIC	PRODUCT
HfC	3880°C	Nippon Carbon	Hi-Nicalon
Zr/C	3540°C	UBE Industries	Typranno
Hf/B ₂	3380°C	COIC	Sylramic
Hf/N	3305°C	OX	PRODUCT
Zr/B ₂	3245°C	3M	Nextel
		Nippon Carbon	Hi-Nicalon
CMC		PREPEG	
CC	2000-3000°C	OxOx	PRODUCT
C/SiC	1350-2100°C	Axiom	AX-780037900
SiC/SiC	1100-1600°C		CerFace surfacing film
Ox/Ox	1000-1200°C		

Oxide-Oxide CMCs increased

<Oxide vs Other composites materials research>

[1] NITE, "What is NITE Process?" [Online]. Available: <https://nite.co.jp/what-is-nite-process-2/>.

[2] Le, Vinh Tung, Ngoc San Ha, and Nam Seo Goo. "Advanced sandwich structures for thermal protection systems in hypersonic vehicles: A review." *Composites Part B: Engineering* 226 (2021): 109301.

Background

❖ Very low earth orbit (VLEO) environment

Benefit

- Reduced launch cost
- Reduced communication latency
- Self-cleaning orbit (large constellation)

Challenge

- Exposure to atomic oxygen (AO)
- Atmospheric drag
- Fuel consumption

<Resolution comparison^[4]>

< Self-cleaning orbit^[5]>

< Large constellation^[5]>

<Damage to an ISS solar array by AO exposure^[6]>

LEO environment & VLEO environment^[3]

Condition	LEO environment	VLEO environment
Altitude	450 ~ 2,000 km	160 ~ 450 km
AO flux	$10^{12} \sim 10^{13}$ atoms/cm ² · s	$10^{14} \sim 10^{15}$ atoms/cm ² · s
Atmospheric density	10^{-12} kg/m ³	10^{-9} kg/m ³
Vacuum	$10^{-6} \sim 10^{-10}$ Torr	$10^{-5} \sim 10^{-6}$ Torr
Temperature	-150 ~ 150°C	-150 ~ 150°C
Heat cycle	90~110 min	90~110 min
UV radiation	100 ~ 400 nm	100 ~ 400 nm

[3] Han, Joo-Hyun, and Chun-Gon Kim. "Low earth orbit space environment simulation and its effects on graphite/epoxy composites." *Composite structures* 72.2 (2006): 218-226.

[4] Chen, Guoquan, et al. "VLEO Satellite Constellation Design for Regional Aviation and Marine Coverage." *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering* (2023).

[5] Llop, J. Virgili, et al. "Very low earth orbit mission concepts for earth observation: Benefits and challenges." *Reinventing Space Conference*. 2014.

[6] Kimoto, Yugo, et al. "MDM: a flight mission to observe materials degradation in-situ on satellite in super low Earth orbit." *Acta Astronautica* 179 (2021): 695-701.

Background

❖ Discharge wall of the hall effect thruster

Discharge wall must satisfy the requirements: high-temperature resistance, thermal shock resistance, high thermal conductivity low thermal expansion, and dielectric properties^[8]

<GOCE satellite>

<Plasma thruster discharge walls^[7]>

<Discharge wall surface erosion induced by Xe⁺ ions in plasma thrusters^[6]>

<Surface degradation of plasma thruster discharge walls^[7]>

Discharge wall erosion rate^[8]

$$\varepsilon = j_{i\perp} Y(E, \theta)$$

$$E = E_{plasma} + E_{sheath}$$

$$E_{plasma} = E_{plasma}(\Delta\phi_{plasma})$$

$$Y = \left(0.0099 + \alpha^2 6.04 \times 10^{-6} - \alpha^3 4.75 \times 10^{-8}\right) \sqrt{\varepsilon_i} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{58.6}{\varepsilon_i}}\right)^{2.5}$$

$$\Delta\phi_{plasma} = \phi_d - \phi_{sheath\ edge}$$

$$E_{sheath} = E_{sheath}(\Delta\phi_{sheath})$$

$$\Delta\phi_{sheath} = \Delta\phi_{sheath}(T_e)$$

Sigmund theory^[8]

$$Y(E) \approx \alpha \frac{S_n(E)}{U_o}$$

$Y(E) = \text{Sputtering yield}$
 $S_n(E) = \text{Nuclear stopping power}$
 $\alpha = \text{Correction factor}$
 $U_o = \text{Surface binding energy}$

[6] Mikellides, I. G., Katz, I., Hofer, R. R., and Goebel, D. M., "Design of a Laboratory Hall Thruster with Magnetically Shielded Channel Walls, Phase III: Comparison of Theory with Experiment," AIAA-2012-3789, July 2012

[7] Precision Ceramics. (n.d.). Boron nitride uses in Hall effect ion thrusters

Literature survey (1/5)

❖ Magnetically shielded hall thruster

Magnetically shielded Hall thrusters reduce discharge wall erosion but may reduce anode efficiency and thrust by about 20% under the same operating conditions

<Plasma temperature according to thruster type^[6]>

Thruster Configuration	Temperature (c)
US (Inner)	500
US(Outer)	510
MS (Inner)	422
MS(Outer)	447

<Comparison between the thrust, anode efficiency of the US and MS thrusters with ceramic wall^[8]>

< BN-SiO₂ and graphite left: thrust, right: anode efficiency^[8]>

<Hall plasma discharge wall materials left: BN, right: graphite^[8]>

[8] Grimaud, Lou, and Stéphane Mazouffre. "Performance comparison between standard and magnetically shielded 200 W Hall thrusters with BN-SiO₂ and graphite channel walls." *Vacuum* 155 (2018): 514-523.

Literature survey (2/5)

❖ BN–CaO–Y₂O₃–Al₂O₃ of plasma resistance

The sputtering damage of h-BN grains by Xe ions includes B–N bond breaking and layer delamination, while composite erosion involves joint damage with mullite and separation of h-BN grains from the surface

Lattice distortion

<Test direction of sample^[10]>

<Micro morphology of textured ceramics before and after etching^[10]>

<Phase analysis results of sample surface before and after etching^[10]>
 <Mass etching rate (M_m) and line etching rate (M_l) of textured ceramics^[10]>

No	Mass etching rate	Line etching rate
1-TS	1.15	4.96
1-SS	1.19	5.14
2-TS	1.05	4.53
2-SS	1.09	4.71
4-TS	1.16	4.99
4-SS	1.15	4.93

<Damage model of h-BN crystal by Xe ion etching^[10]>

[10] Tian, Zhuo, et al. "Etching resistance and etching behavior of h-BN textured ceramics under Xe plasma condition." *Ceramics International* 48.7 (2022): 9099-9106.

Literature survey (3/5)

❖ Y_2O_3 -based ceramics etching by Xe plasma

Y_2O_3 -based composites exhibit enhanced plasma erosion resistance with increasing Al_2O_3 content, owing to improved densification and reduced grain detachment

<Phase composition of the sintered material>

<Etching surface 3D images by AFM microscope^[9]>

<Surface morphology before and after etching and energy spectrum analysis (YAGA). a) before b) after c) energy spectrum of A grains; d) energy spectrum of B grains^[9]>

<Schematic of the mechanism of the plasma etching process for sintered ceramics>

Literature survey (4/5)

❖ AO damage mechanism of ZrC-C/C composites

The performance evolution of ZrC-C/C composite under AO exposure involves two stages including the improvement stage, substantial damage stage

< Non-exposed, Exposed C/C composite^[11]>

<Schematic diagram of the AO damage process on ZrC-C/C^[11]>

Literature survey (5/5)

❖ AO erosion resistance on Al_2O_3/SiO_2 film coated PI

<(a) FESEM of $Al_2O_3/SiO_2@PI$ (b) AFM of 30 nm $Al_2O_3/SiO_2@PI$ (c) Cross-section of $SiO_2@PI$ (d) Cross-section of $Al_2O_3/SiO_2@PI$ >

<FTIR spectra of PI, $SiO_2@PI$, and $Al_2O_3/SiO_2@PI$ before and after AO>

<Schematic of AO beam erosion path through $ALD-SiO_2@PI$ and $ALD-Al_2O_3/SiO_2@PI$ >

<FESEM images and EDS element mapping of PI after AO erosion>

<XPS spectrum analysis of $ALD@PI$ surface before and after AO irradiation: Surface elemental contents>

Research highlights

VLEO satellite

VLEO environment
Atomic oxygen
Thermal cycle
UV light
Vacuum

Plasma

“Develop a new concept of plasma thruster discharge wall using Ox/Ox CMCs”

Conventional Methods

- Low costs
- Low temperatures
- Low pressures
- High mechanical properties
- Autoclave curing (Slurry methods) etc.

Proposed Methods of Oxide/Oxide Ceramic Matrix Composites

“New method of Ox/Ox CMCs for plasma thruster discharge wall”

II. Materials preparation

Materials preparation

❖ Ceramic oxide fiber

<Ceramic roving>

- Metal oxide-based material (99%)
- Low secondary electron emission (SEE)
- Low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE)
- High-temperature resistance
- High-plasma resistance

<Surface energy by type of composites^[12~14]>

Sample	Surface free energy [mN/m]
Ox-Ox composites^[14]	50 ~ 70
CFRP ^[13]	30
GFRP ^[12]	30

❖ Ceramic oxide matrix

<Ceramic powder>

<Alkali + Water>

<XRD and FTIR results for Oxide/Oxide CMCs>

<Structural oxide ceramic network^[14]>

[12] Jia, Dechang, et al. Geopolymer and geopolymer matrix composites. Singapore: Springer, 2020.

[13] Aliheidari, et al. "Retaining high fracture toughness in aged polymer Composite/adhesive joints through optimization of plasma surface treatment." Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing 176 (2024): 107835.

[14] Yang, Chengjuan, et al. "Functionalized CFRP surface with water-repellence, self-cleaning and anti-icing properties." Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects 586 (2020): 124278.

Materials preparation

❖ Fabrication of Oxide/Oxide CMCs

Ceramic oxide matrix

Oxide/Oxide ceramic matrix composites

III. Methods

Method

❖ VLEO space environment simulated facility

- Chamber size (inside): 600×500×250 mm
- Atomic oxygen generator: DC supply & Ion beam gun
- Atomic oxygen flux: 1.35×10^{17} atoms/cm²·s
- Ultraviolet (UV) lamp: 280 ~ 420 nm
- Thermal cycle: -80 ~ 150 °C / 90 min/cycle
- Max temperature 1,000 °C
- Vacuum: 10⁻⁷ Torr

<Schematic of VLEO space chamber>

VLEO space environment simulated facility @ KAU

<VLEO space chamber @KAU MCML Lab>

Method

❖ Plasma test conditions

- Materials: Ox/Ox CMCs, h-BN, Al₂O₃
- Gas: Argon
- Gas flow rate: 10 SCCM
- Time: 4 Hours
- Angle: 0°^[16]
- Beam energy: 1,000 eV

❖ VLEO space environment test conditions

- Materials: Ox/Ox CMCs
- Atomic oxygen: 1.35×10^{17} atoms /cm²·s
- Thermal cycle: -80 ~ 150°C / 90 min
- Vacuum: 1×10^{-6} Torr
- UV lamp: 280 ~ 420 nm
- Exposure time: 0, 7.5, 15, 24 Hours

<VLEO space environment test >

IV. Results and discussion

Results and discussion

❖ Results of the VLEO environment test

< XRD patterns and FT-IR spectra of Ox/Ox CMCs after VLEO environment exposure >

0 h 7.5 h 15 h 24 h

$$E = \frac{\Delta M}{MFA_s}$$

$\Delta M = \text{mass loss}$
 $A_s = \text{AO action area}$
 $F = \text{AO fluence}$
 $M = \text{AO average mass}$

VLEO space environment exposure time(1h/7days)

<Results of tensile test> <Erosion rate of oxide/oxide composites>

No.	Materials	Erosion rate
This study	Ox-Ox composite	0.02
Liu et al. [16]	SiC-Carbon/Carbon	-0.02
Luan et al. [17]	Carbon/SiC-HfC	0.22
Liu et al. [18]	TaC-Carbon/Carbon	0.23
Zhai et al. [19]	Carbon/CE	0.425
Choi et al. [20]	OG POSS/epoxy	1.0
Han et al. [21]	Graphite/Epoxy	1.5

<SEM images after exposure to the VLEO environment>

[16] Liu, Guanghai, et al. "Damage behavior of atomic oxygen on zirconium carbide coating modified carbon/carbon composite." Ceramics International 46.3 (2020): 3324-3331
 [17] Damage behavior of atomic oxygen on a hafnium carbide-modified C/ SiC composite
 [18] Atomic oxygen damage behavior of TaC coating-modified C/C composite

Results and discussion

❖ Results of the plasma etching test

<Results of density>

Sample	Density (g/m ³)
This study	2.85
h-BN	1.9
Alumina	3.9

<Alumina before> <Alumina after>

<h-BN before> <h-BN after>

<Ox/Ox CMCs before> <Ox/Ox CMCs after>

< Analysis of the AFM >

<Results of erosion rate for plasma>

< Results of XRD of plasma etching test >

< Results of XPS of plasma etching test >

[19] Synergistic effects of atomic oxygen and thermal cycling in low earth orbit on polymer-matrixed space materia
 [20] Enhanced resistance to atomic oxygen of OG POSS/epoxy nanocomposites
 [21] Low earth orbit space environment simulation and its effects on graphite/epoxy composites

V. Conclusions

Conclusions

- In this study, we conducted space environment assessments and thermal shock evaluations to develop a new concept discharge wall for a plasma thruster operating in VLEO.
- The evaluation of the VLEO environment showed no significant changes in chemical structure or tensile strength after prolonged exposure to atomic oxygen.
- Plasma erosion tests showed that the material had a higher erosion rate than Boron Nitride Grade HP, and no phase transformation was observed.
- **In future works**, the investigation will be expanded to evaluate structural integrity under plasma-exposed conditions.

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